

The First International Conference on Smarandache Multispace and Multistructure was held in China

In recent decades, Smarandache's notions of multispace and multistructure were widely spread and have shown much importance in sciences around the world. Organized by Prof. Linfan Mao, a professional conference on multispaces and multistructures, named the *First International Conference on Smarandache Multispace and Multistructure* was held in Beijing University of Civil Engineering and Architecture of P. R. China on June 28-30, 2013, which was announced by American Mathematical Society in advance.

The Smarandache multispace and multistructure are qualitative notions, but both can be applied to metric and non-metric systems. There were 46 researchers have taken part in this conference with 14 papers on Smarandache multispaces and geometry, birings, neutrosophy, neutrosophic groups, regular maps and topological graphs with applications to non-solvable equation systems.

Prof. Yanpei Liu reports on topological graphs

Prof. Linfan Mao reports on non-solvable systems of equations

Prof. Shaofei Du reports on regular maps with developments

Applications of Smarandache multispaces and multistructures underline a combinatorial mathematical structure and interchangeability with other sciences, including gravitational fields, weak and strong interactions, traffic network, etc.

All participants have showed a genuine interest on topics discussed in this conference and would like to carry these notions forward in their scientific works.

The conference's announcement in Chinese language:

首届 Smarandache 重空间与重结构学术交流会召开

<http://www.bucea.edu.cn/xzdt/45363.htm>